

Open Access: Position of the Swiss Academies of Arts and Sciences

The Swiss Academies of Arts and Sciences and its members support the principle of Open Access with the goal to provide free access to scientific publications. Within their networks, they act as an intermediary between member organisations and policy institutions in the promotion of research.

General Principles

The Swiss Academies of Arts and Sciences

- Make their publications available immediately and free of charge (Diamond Open Access) and thus guarantee lasting accessibility.
- Support the National Open-Access-Strategy by swissuniversities and the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) for Switzerland.
- Support the statement by the All European Academies (ALLEA) on Plan S, according to which the scientific community needs to be involved for its concrete implementation.

Measures of Promotion

The Swiss Academies of Arts and Sciences

- Ensure free access to the publications they subsidise. In the case of periodicals, they aim to ensure that authors have free access to their articles after 12 months at the latest (Green Open Access). As far as possible, they support more extensive Open Access models (Gold and Diamond Open Access from flipping journals).
- Are in exchange with (Swiss) publishers on Open Access and discuss feasible publication models together.
- Support alternative publication platforms and collaborate with higher education institutions and libraries, e.g. with Bern Open Publishing (BOP, University of Berne) and the Main Library Open Publishing Environment (HOPE, University of Zurich).
- Make their expertise in publishing, especially regarding scientific periodicals, available to relevant bodies. In their networks they promote the understanding of Open Access in suitable formats (events, workshops, publications, etc.) and support discipline-appropriate forms of publication.

Measures of Support

The Swiss Academies of Arts and Sciences

- Deal with international developments in Open Access, examine their implications on publishing in Switzerland in their area of funding and support the implementation of innovative initiatives.
- Promote (re)-use of their publications via permanent identifiers (e.g. DOI) and Open Access-Licences (CC BY or CC BY SA).

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